

Identification of Invasive Alien Species using DNA barcodes

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
Rue Vautier 29,
1000 Brussels, Belgium
+32 (0)2 627 41 23

Royal Museum for Central Africa
Leuvensesteenweg 13,
3080 Tervuren, Belgium
+32 (0)2 769 58 54

General introduction to this factsheet

The Barcoding Facility for Organisms and Tissues of Policy Concern (BopCo) aims at developing an expertise forum to facilitate the identification of biological samples of policy concern in Belgium and Europe. The project represents part of the Belgian federal contribution to the European Research Infrastructure Consortium LifeWatch.

Non-native species which are being introduced into Europe, whether by accident or deliberately, can be of policy concern since some of them can reproduce and disperse rapidly in a new territory, establish viable populations and even outcompete native species. As a consequence of their presence, natural and managed ecosystems can be disrupted, crops and livestock affected, and vector-borne diseases or parasites might be introduced, impacting human health and socio-economic activities. Non-native species causing such adverse effects are called Invasive Alien Species (IAS). In order to protect native biodiversity and ecosystems, and to mitigate the potential impact on human health and socio-economic activities, the issue of IAS is tackled in Europe by EU Regulation 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and Council. The IAS Regulation provides for a set of measures to be taken across all member states. The list of Invasive Alien Species of Union Concern is regularly updated. In order to implement the proposed actions, however, methods for accurate species identification are required when suspicious biological material is encountered.

Because morphology-based species identifications are not always possible (e.g. cryptic species, trace material, early life-stages), the purpose of the present work is to investigate and evaluate the usefulness of DNA sequence data to identify each of the IAS included in the EU Regulation. The results are presented as factsheets (one per IAS) compiled using publicly available DNA sequence data and information aggregated from various sources. Each factsheet consists of two major parts; (i) a short introduction to the specific IAS compiling information on its taxonomy and current occurrence/distribution in Europe; (ii) an investigation with respect to the usefulness of publicly available DNA sequences to identify this IAS to the taxonomic level stated in the EU list using DNA barcoding. For further information about the reasoning behind the applied approach and details on the materials and methods utilised, please see below and Smitz *et al.* [1].

More info about BopCo on <http://bopco.myspecies.info/> or contact us via bopco@naturalsciences.be
More info on the EU Regulation on http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/invasivealien/index_en.htm

Baccharis halimifolia

L., 1753

Common names:

English: eastern baccharis, groundsel baccharis, groundsel bush, seepwillow, silverling, sea myrtle, manglier, consumption weed, saltbush

French: baccharide à feuilles d'halime, séneçon en arbre

German: gewöhnlicher Kreuzstrauch

Dutch: struikaster, kruisstruik

Last update: August 2018

General information on *Baccharis halimifolia*

Classification

Kingdom	Phylum	Clade	Order	Family	Genus
Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Eudicots	Asterales	Asteraceae	<i>Baccharis</i>

Species in the same genus: N = 354-400 [2-4]

Note: *Baccharis halimifolia* and some 28 species, depending on the author, are placed in the subgenus *Baccharis*.

Infra-species level: N = 0

Note: To our knowledge, no subspecies or varieties have been described.

Native range: [5-7]

North America (Canada and United States of America) to Central America (Caribbean and Mexico).

Invasive range: [7, 8]

Europe (geographical):

Belgium, France, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, United Kingdom.

For more detailed locality information and the most recent distribution updates, please visit:

www.gbif.org/species/3129663

<https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/BACHA/distribution>

www.europe-aliens.org/speciesFactsheet.do?speciesId=22356#

Outside Europe (geographical):

Australia, Georgia, New Zealand.

Morphology, biology, invasion, negative effects and remedies

For more information on *Baccharis halimifolia* please see the references and online information listed at the end of this document.

Species identification based on DNA barcodes

Introduction

DNA barcoding is a species identification method that uses a short genetic sequence (DNA barcode) to compare an unknown sample to a database of reference sequences with known species affiliations. The underlying rationale is that the divergence of nucleotide sequences among different species is larger than the nucleotide divergence between sequences within a species. DNA barcoding can facilitate the identification of IAS samples, especially when morphological characteristics are absent or useless. To assure correct species identifications, however, reference libraries need to include a sufficiently large number of sequences of (i) the IAS under investigation, in order to assess the intraspecific genetic divergence; (ii) the closely related species, in order to evaluate the interspecific genetic divergence; (iii) the different geographical areas covering the distribution range (native and invasive) of the IAS in order to detect potential population structure or local hybrids.

Against this background, BopCo evaluated the inclusion of the IAS and their close relatives in both publicly available reference libraries BOLD (www.boldsystems.org/) and GenBank (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/) to estimate the reliability with which a species identification can be obtained using DNA barcoding.

Material and Methods [1]

Download all sequence data available for the genus

Filtering the data and selecting 'promising' markers

Aligning and trimming of the sequences

Building Neighbour-Joining tree with Bootstrap support

Conclusion:

Based on the present evaluation of the available sequence data, no DNA marker can be used to identify *Baccharis halimifolia*. However, a 2014 study indicates that (a combination of) markers ETS, ITS, psbA-trnH and trnL seem promising to further investigate once the sequence data becomes available.

Discussion

DNA markers for which *Baccharis* sequences were available, were downloaded from GenBank and BOLD for all represented species of the genus *Baccharis*. Three DNA markers were evaluated (Table 1). The *Baccharis* congeners are poorly represented online (Table 2); of the over 350 accepted species only 14 have sequence data available in the repositories.

None of the DNA markers evaluated (**matK**, **rbcl** and **ITS2**) recovered *B. halimifolia* as a supported cluster. The markers show little genetic variation for genus *Baccharis* and are ineffective in differentiating *B. halimifolia* from the other species. In the current state of the online reference libraries it is not advisable to apply these markers for species identification.

For the **psbA-trnH** intergenic spacer and the **trnL** gene with **trnL-trnF** intergenic spacer very few sequences are available and the markers show little genetic variation among the different species. Therefore it is currently impossible to assess the ability of these markers to identify *B. halimifolia*.

In 2014, Heiden [9] published a phylogenetic hypothesis for the classification of subgenus lineages within *Baccharis* by including 248 species and concatenating the sequences of four DNA markers (**ETS**, **ITS**, **trnH-psbA**, **trnL-trnF**). The results indicate that a combination of the four markers looks promising for differentiation among taxa, at least at the subgenus level. This dataset would add immensely to the number of species represented, but is not publicly available yet. Consequently the DNA markers could not be evaluated here and it is impossible to assess the ability of these DNA markers, individually or in combination, to identify *B. halimifolia*.

Table 1: Overview of the encountered issues concerning the DNA-based identification of the IAS [1]: (1) Insufficient publicly available DNA sequences of the IAS to capture the intra-species divergence; (2) Poor geographical coverage of the IAS sequences (native or invasive range missing); (3) The IAS sequences do not form supported clusters; (4) Potential misidentification of a specimen which influences the clustering of the IAS sequences; and (5) Not all congeneric species are represented in the final NJ-tree. An 'X' indicates that the issue was encountered, a '1' indicates only one *B. halimifolia* sequence was available.

Markers analysed	1	2	3	4	5
rbcl		X	X		X
matK	X	X	X		X
ITS2	X	X	1		X

Table 2: Publicly available sequences downloaded (July 2018) from BOLD and GenBank (including sequences extracted from plastid genomes) which were withheld as reliable and informative in the final alignment that was used for building the NJ-trees. The species names follow [4]. An 'X' indicates that at least one sequence was used in the final alignment.

Species in genus	rbcl	matK	ITS2
<i>Baccharis angustifolia</i>	X	X	
<i>Baccharis boliviensis</i>			X
<i>Baccharis brachyphylla</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis dracunculifolia</i>			X
<i>Baccharis genistelloides</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis glomeruliflora</i>	X	X	
<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis inamoena</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis neglecta</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis pedunculata</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis salicina</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis sarothroides</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis sergiloides</i>	X		X
<i>Baccharis tricuneata</i>	X	X	X
<i>Baccharis vanessae</i>	X	X	X
TOTAL species	14 /354-400	13 /354-400	14 /354-400

For a more elaborate discussion of the available databases, the sequence selection process, the outcome of the NJ-tree analyses, the usefulness of the investigated DNA sequences for species identification, as well as information on how to send samples for analyses please contact BopCo directly.

References and online information

Online information

http://www.efloras.org/florataxon.aspx?flora_id=1&taxon_id=103317
http://www.q-bank.eu/Plants/Factsheets/Baccharis_halimifolia_EN.pdf
https://plants.usda.gov/factsheet/pdf/fs_baha.pdf
<http://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/8164>

Picture credits

Page 1: *Baccharis halimifolia* 2c By Consultaplantas [CC BY-SA 4.0]
Page 2 (left, top): Saltbush (*Baccharis halimifolia*) (8151781706) By Bob Peterson [CC BY-SA 2.0]
Page 2 (left, bottom): *Baccharis_halimifolia_004_php* By Steve Hurst (USDA-NRCS PLANTS Database) [Public domain]
Page 2 (middle): Groundsel Bush By Paul Cooper [CC BY-NC 2.0]
Page 2 (right): *Baccharis_halimifolia_1120477* By James H. Miller & Ted Bodner, Southern Weed Science Society, Bugwood.org [CC BY 3.0]

References

- [1] N. Smitz, S. Gombeer, K. Meganck, A. Vanderheyden, Y. R. Van Bourgonie, T. Backeljau, and M. De Meyer, "Identifying IAS based on DNA barcoding using currently available sequence data: details on applied material and methods." 2019. [Online]. Available from: <http://bopco.myspecies.info/content/invasive-alien-species-ias-factsheets>.
- [2] G. Heiden and J. R. Pirani, "Novelties towards a phylogenetic infrageneric classification of *Baccharis* (Asteraceae, Astereae)," *Phytotaxa*, vol. 289, no. 3, pp. 285–290, 2016.
- [3] D. A. Giuliano, "New Infragenera in *Baccharis* (Asteraceae, Astereae)," *Novon*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 534–541, 2005.
- [4] "The Plant List. Version 1.1," *Published on the Internet*, 2013. [Online]. Available: www.theplantlist.org/. [Accessed: 15-Feb-2018].
- [5] L. Caño, J. A. Campos, D. García-Magro, and M. Herrera, "Replacement of estuarine communities by an exotic shrub: Distribution and invasion history of *Baccharis halimifolia* in Europe," *Biol. Invasions*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1183–1188, 2013.
- [6] "*Baccharis halimifolia* Management Manual," Ihobe – Public Environmental Management Company, BilBao.
- [7] G. Fried, L. Caño, S. Brunel, E. Beteta, A. Charpentier, M. Herrera, U. Starfinger, and F. Dane Panetta, "Monographs on invasive plants in Europe: *Baccharis halimifolia* L.," *Bot. Lett.*, vol. 163, no. 2, pp. 127–153, 2016.
- [8] G. Rappé, F. Verloove, W. Vanlanduyt, and W. Vercruyssen, "*Baccharis halimifolia* (Asteraceae) aan de Belgische kust," *Dumortiera*, vol. 82, pp. 17–26, 2004.
- [9] G. Heiden, "Systematics of *Baccharis* (Asteraceae: Astereae)," Biblioteca Digital de Teses e Dissertações da Universidad de São Paulo, São Paulo, 2014.

To cite this factsheet, please use

Barcoding Facility for Organisms and Tissues of Policy Concern, 2019. Factsheet on *Baccharis halimifolia*; July 2018. In: Identification of Invasive Alien Species using DNA barcodes. BopCo, Belgium. Available from: www.bopco.myspecies.info/content/invasive-alien-species-ias-factsheets, accessed on DD-MM-YYYY.

DISCLAIMER: The information represented in this factsheet has been compiled from many different sources. Every reasonable effort has been made to ensure that the material presented is accurate and reflects the current (see date last update) scientific knowledge. However, recent changes in e.g. taxonomy and distribution, or the publication of additional reference sequences may not be implemented. The views which are expressed in the "Conclusion" are those of the author(s) and have not been peer-reviewed. BopCo does not guarantee the accuracy of the data included in this factsheet. The content of the factsheet is for information only and is not intended as legal advice. BopCo may not be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. If you should notice any issues considering the content of this factsheet, or if you would like to contribute any additional information to it, please contact us through bopco@naturalsciences.be.

